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The teacher's attitude towards students with sen from a socio-ecological perspective

Abstract: A teacher's attitude towards students with SEN is recognized by a number of authors as a decisive component in ensuring the successful inclusion of these students. The article addresses the issues of the teacher's attitude towards students with SEN from a socioecological perspective. The

teacher's attitude towards students with SEN (based on individual characteristics) is explored in relation to the microsystem (relationships with parents and peers), the mesosystem (school organizational culture and resources, adapted curriculum, and pedagogical practices and experiences), the exosystem (community social norms and culture, infrastructure, and services), and the macrosystem (policies and laws). The article reflects the key points of the socio-ecological framework of the teacher's attitude, based on an analysis of literature and on research. The findings form a background for further practical interventions.

Keywords: teacher's attitude, socioecological perspective, students with SEN.

Rezumat: Atitudinea profesorilor față de elevii cu CES este recunoscută de mai mulți autori ca o componentă decisivă în asigurarea incluziunii de succes a acestor elevi. Articolul abordează problematica atitudinii profesorului față de elevii cu CES din perspectivă socioecologică. Atitudinea profesorului față de elevii cu CES (pe baza caracteristicilor individuale) este explorată în raport cu microsistemul (relațiile cu părinții și semenii), mezosistemul (cultura și resursele organizaționale școlare, curriculumul adaptat, practicile și experiențele pedagogice), exosistemul (normele și cultura socială comunitară, infrastructura și serviciile) și macrosistemul (politici și legi). Articolul reflectă punctele-cheie ale cadrului socioecologic al atitudinii profesorului pe baza

unei analize a literaturii și cercetărilor. Subiectul constituie fundalul intervențiilor practice.

Cuvinte-cheie: atitudinea profesorului, perspectivă socioecologică, elevi cu CES.

Despite the fact that the adoption of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2006) has stimulated research and policy development, approximately 5.1 million children with disabilities across Europe and Central Asia still face multiple rights violations [3]. Among multiple problems, current studies in the field have noted the problem of stigmatizing attitudes towards children with disabilities [4; 5]. Several studies have provided evidence that the negative attitudes of teachers towards students with disabilities are a major barrier to student learning [6; 7; 8].

At the same time, school climate includes six factors: supportive leadership; teachers' autonomy; prestige of the teaching profession; renovations; teachers' collaboration; and workload. Examination of the intercorrelations among these factors and with attitudes revealed that those teachers who perceived their school as having a supportive leadership, encouraging renovations and collaboration and not threatening teachers' autonomy tended to express more positive attitudes towards inclusion [9].

The experience in educating children with special education needs (SEN) brings a change in attitude. Formation of attitude is influenced by several factors. As the current role of the teacher has changed from that of merely imparting knowledge or being the exclusive source of knowledge to the more challenging role of being rather a guide or facilitator for the search for relevant information and ways of self-development, new ways of developing unfamiliar skills need to be found.

Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory approaches child development as a complex system of relationships that intersect at multiple levels of the environment, such as the microsystem, the mesosystem, the exosystem, the macrosystem, and the chronosystem [1]. In the context of our research, we would like to explore the five-layered model of the socio-ecological framework with the relevant components in relation to the teacher's attitude towards students with SEN (Figure 1). The central point of the system is the student with SEN with specific characteristics (sex, age, health, type of disability, motivation etc.).

Many researchers have examined the relationship between different types of attitudes and variables such as teacher age (Mdikana, Ntshagangase, & Mayekiso, 2007), gender (Sharma & Desai, 2002), teaching experience (Marston & Leslie, 1983), educational preparation (Mangope, Koyabe, & Mukhopadhyay, 2012), and type and severity of student disability (Rizzo & Vispoel, 1991) [apud 7].

The teacher's attitudes towards students with SEN (based on individual characteristics) should be explored in relation to the microsystem. The microsystem encompasses the relationships and interactions a student

with SEN has with immediate surroundings, such as family, teachers, peers with disabilities and nondisabled. The basis of the child's development is created in the family. The family is the primary unit that encourages the student to have confidence in himself and to move forward in life, regardless of impediments. A teacher's positive attitude can also help students with SEN gain confidence and learning motivation. The acceptance of students with SEN by nondisabled peers in joint activities can also encourage them to learn. At the same time, often acceptance depends on teachers' attitude.

The mesosystem ensures the connection between the structures of the microsystem of students with SEN. In this regard, we note the connection of teachers' positive attitude with such structures as a school's inclusive organizational culture and resources, a school's capacity to offer a safe and friendly space to students, the existence of an adapted curriculum for the needs of students with SEN.

Specifically, some authors mention practices and experiences that work with students with SEN: the attitude of teachers who have worked with children with SEN towards inclusion is different from that of their colleagues who have not worked with such children [2]. When teachers have many contacts with disabled persons, their attitudes and ability to teach disabled children are influenced [6]. Teachers who personally support inclusive practice and accept the concept of inclusion can more readily adapt the learning environment to the diverse needs of students and use a variety of approaches and teaching strategies [8].

Figure 1. *The socio-ecological framework of teachers' attitudes towards students with SEN*

Teachers' attitudes towards inclusion often depend both on the confrontations between their professional commitment and doubts about their competencies, but also on how the educational system is prepared to support them [5]. Other factors that influence their attitude towards inclusion should be mentioned, such as the implementation of inclusion at the school, sources of support, the distribution of resources, the availability of support from the school administration and colleagues, the organization framework etc.

Recent studies [2; 4; 5] and our professional experience have emphasized the importance of teacher training that prepares the teachers for inclusion and gives them more professional expertise, because this prepares them better for work with children with SEN, boosts their self-confidence, and helps them develop a more positive attitude towards such children.

The exosystem defines the larger social system that includes some structures without a direct connection with teachers' attitudes, but with an important impact on the formation of the inclusive environment, which can favor the formation of inclusive attitudes. Respectively, the exosystem should include inclusive community social norms and culture, infrastructure, transport, and services adapted to needs of students with SEN; community support to families with students with SEN etc.

The macrosystem includes the overarching culture that influences the development of students with SEN and the teachers' attitude towards them. Cultural contexts are interconnected with socioeconomic status/context, ethnicity, religion, and geographic location. A special role belongs to the policies and laws that cover the subject. Thus, the adoption of inclusive policies and laws contributes to the formation of an inclusive culture. Their lack can generate discrimination and exclusion. At the same time, in case decision-makers force inclusion in schools without creating relevant conditions (connection with other systems), this risks causing the teachers to develop negative attitudes towards students with SEN. As a result, it can decrease students' motivation to learn, which could have negative social consequences in the future.

The *chronosystem* consists of changing socio-historical circumstances and the transition of events over the life course. An example of changing socio-historical circumstances is the increase in opportunities for children with disabilities to learn in general schools, together with those without disabilities.

In conclusion: Based on literature analysis, we conclude that the teachers' attitude may be considered as one of the significant components in the inclusion of students with SEN in the education process. The Ecological Systems Theory, which provides a holistic approach by including various systems, can be a valuable

and useful framework in educational practice.

To understand the impact of the teachers' attitudes towards students with SEN on such students' development, it is essential to focus on students with specific needs, on the teachers' personalities, on the development context (factors and structures of the systems mentioned above), as well as development results, because these processes vary and affect students and teachers differently.

The world is constantly changing, not least due to technological developments. This is why the factors and structures in the mentioned systems must be approached with great care. For example, the exosystem and macrosystem could be expanded to take into account influences from social media, video games, and other modern interactions.

All these things suggest that ecological systems are still valid and may be extended over time, adjusted by new components to include new modern developments.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES:

1. Bronfenbrenner U. Ecological Systems Theory. In: Vasta R. (ed.) *Annals of Child Development*, Vol. 6, 1989. London, UK: Jessica Kingsley Publishers, pp. 187-249.
2. Cara A. Implementarea educației incluzive în Republica Moldova: Studiu de politici publice. Chișinău: Lexon-Prim, 2015. 60 p.
3. Desk Review for Developing Measures on Discriminatory Attitudes and Social Norms towards Children with Disabilities in Europe and Central Asia Region, 2018. UNICEF, 2019, 51 p. On: <https://www.unicef.org/eca/media/13391/file>
4. Global Education Monitoring Report, 2020: Inclusion and Education: All Means All. UNESCO, 2020. 502 p.
5. Inclusive Teaching: Preparing All Teachers to Teach All Students. Policy paper 43. UNESCO, 2020, 16 p.
6. Ince S. Preschool Teacher Candidates' Attitudes and Concerns about Inclusive Education, Taking into Consideration whether They Took Special Courses or Not at University. In: *International Journal of Early Childhood Education and Research*, 2012, 1 (3), pp. 1-19. On: <http://ijecer.net/pfi-depo/v1n3/seyda.pdf>
7. Martins C. Inclusive Physical Education: Teachers' Attitudes. University of Vigo, Spain, Porto Alegre, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 637-656.
8. Ryan T. Inclusive Attitude: A Pre-service Analysis. In: *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, Vol. 9, No. 3, 2009, pp. 180-187.
9. Weisel A, Dror O. School Climate, Sense of Efficacy and Israeli Teachers' Attitudes toward Inclusion of Students with Special Needs. In: *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, Vol. 1 (2), 2006, pp. 157-174.